

FLÂNEUR123

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Carton123 architecten

‘Explorations & Cartographies’ – it is simply not possible for an architect to resist such a call. There is this ever present need to know where we are, where we might go, and why. It is the ‘terra incognita’ of an architect’s mind, at the very start of every project. The joy of possible discoveries and the urge for control make a great combination.

The title of the call was the promise for a delightful adventure, a mind-stretching exercise. It soon became clear that the goal was not to simply draw a map of our practice. We did however take on the attitude of a cartographer : exploring, looking closely and scouting. The findings were described afterwards, a set of office discoveries was drawn.

They were the starting point for ‘The not so clean desk’, a 9-minute video presentation, made for the PIR#03 conference. It consists of 162 drawings, accompanied by a spoken text. Twelve of them are shown on the following pages. They were made by Pauline Vermeulen, in close collaboration with Els Van Meerbeek.

In the end, the whole exercise aimed at letting the viewers reflect and connect with a world of imagination. The PIR#03 exploration of our office as unknown territory is not ‘the story of mapping a world’ but rather ‘mapping the world of a story’. Let it be an invitation to imagine other possible stories.

drawings :

(c) Pauline Vermeulen, Carton123, 2021

(c) Joost Raes, boat drawing, 1989

“The principal motive of the wanderspirit is curiosity - the desire to know what is beyond the next turning of the road,

and to probe for oneself the mystery of the names of the places in maps.

In a sub-conscious way the born wanderer is always expecting to come on something very wonderful - beyond the horizon's rim.

The joys of wandering are often balanced by the pains;

but there is something which makes the desire to wander or explore almost incurable in many human beings.”

Graham, Stephen (1927) 'The gentle art of tramping', The Garden City Press: Letchworth, pp. 45

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In Practice

